

IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ARABIC LANGUAGE CLASSES WITH THE HELP OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

Yakubova Firuza Rashidovna

Oriental University,

Teacher of the "Eastern languages" department

Abstract: This article describes the importance of increasing the effectiveness of Arabic language classes based on the use of modern pedagogical technologies, in particular, the importance of boomerang technology in explaining Arabic grammatical rules, and the ways and instructions for its use.

Key words: pedagogy, technology, innovative technology, traditional education, boomerang technology, interactive methods, pedtechnology. educational efficiency.

After our republic gained independence, great changes took place in all spheres, including the sphere of education. In particular, the attitude towards foreign languages has changed dramatically, the demand has increased. Nowadays, every modern student who has a bright vision of his future sets himself the goal of learning foreign languages.

It is known that in the fall of 2011, an international scientific-theoretical conference was held in Moscow on the topic of "Society, Culture, Language". After this conference, all the countries of the world carried out a series of reforms in order to introduce the common language of globalization. In particular, the decision of the President of December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" was adopted with the aim of implementing these reforms in our country [1.]. Within the framework of the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" [2] and the national program of personnel training, a comprehensive system of teaching foreign languages, that is, a harmoniously matured, educated, modern thinker a system aimed at the formation of the young generation and further integration of the republic into the world community was created. Taking into account that the above decision is being implemented today and that foreign language teaching is given great importance, we teachers contribute to the development and prosperity of our country by teaching other languages, including oriental languages, to students who are hungry for

knowledge. we have to swell. As a result of such reforms, the number of young people who have mastered the English language has increased, and they have gained confidence in their knowledge. Now they are not satisfied with English, but they feel the need to learn some other eastern languages.

Therefore, it is important to achieve effectiveness in teaching the Shet language in a time when Uzbek youth grow up like no other, and in a time when proper conditions are created for imparting modern education. So what can be understood by effectiveness in language teaching?

It is known that the word "Efficiency" means "to be useful", "to give a good result" [3]. In order to increase the efficiency of Arabic language classes, the teacher of the Eastern language uses a new pedagogy during his career. using different methods of technologies, it is necessary to update them and constantly improve auxiliary educational tools (visual aids, various pictures, handouts, technical means of teaching). Students' interest in oriental language increases during the lesson organized in this way.

It is known that in the past, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge. It is clear that such a method does not allow students to develop independent thinking, work, creative research, and initiative skills.

Now, as a result of the development of science, technology and innovative technologies, the interest and attention to increase the effectiveness of the lesson by using interactive methods in the educational process is increasing day by day. Trainings using modern technologies in the educational system are aimed at students to find the acquired knowledge by themselves, study it independently, analyze it, evaluate their knowledge, and draw correct conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, and learning of individuals and teams, as well as for them to work and act in mutual cooperation with their fellow students by thinking freely, and at the same time performs the function of management and orientation. During such a lesson, the student becomes a central participant [4;9]

You know many methods, such as cluster, brainstorming, charkhpalak, BBB, fish skeleton, which are widely used in teaching Eastern languages. It should be mentioned here that each teacher can use his personal methods or make changes and additions to the existing technology during the lesson, along with the

pedtechnologies that meet the requirements of world standards, so that it is the level of the group and the talent of the students. related to

Nowadays, most language learners find it difficult to communicate in the language, despite having studied it for many years. Students are shy to speak in front of a group. Often students' speaking levels are not tested and the tests are instead based on grammar. In large groups, it is difficult to give each student enough opportunities to use the language. In order to prevent such actual problems, the organization of the lesson based on interactive methods with effective use of pedtechnologies helps in a certain sense.

1. Depending on the type of task, students can work individually, in pairs or in groups. Boomerang technology can be cited as an example among many pedtechnologies in organizing such an interactive lesson. This technology is mostly used in political and social sciences. But we can also use it to teach oriental languages. Boomerang technology can be used effectively to explain a new topic and to reinforce a previously learned topic.
2. There are large topics in Arabic grammar that combine several rules, such as gender category, point, and adverbial clauses, boomerang technology can be used to explain them.
3. For this, you need to do the following:
 1. Handout material is prepared by the teacher on a certain topic. Then the rules related to the topic or topic are divided into 3-4 parts.
 2. Students are divided into 3-4 groups. For example, there are 4 students in each group.
 3. Group 1 is given the first part of the topic. Each student in the group should have a separate copy. The 2nd group will be given the second part of the topic, the 3-4 groups will be given 3-4 parts.
 4. 10 minutes will be allocated for groups to master the information they have.
 5. After the specified time, one representative from each group goes to the board one by one and explains the information about the given part to other groups, examples are written on the board and commented. As a result, students will be fully acquainted with all parts of the new topic.
 6. The teacher instructs each group to prepare a complex question on the given part.

7. Groups read the prepared questions in turn. Each group says its answer option. 3 points for a group that gave a detailed answer, 2 points for a partial answer. 1 point is given to the group that filled in.

11. Or the question-and-answer session can be conducted in a different way, that is, the questions are read by the teacher, and the groups answer in turn.

12. The teacher monitors the whole process, corrects the mistakes and shortcomings and makes a general conclusion on the topic.

In this pedtechnology, teachers are not in the center, but students are in the center, and teachers only act as assistants or guides to students in mastering the subject. In this, students' ability to work independently will be further developed.

Narrating various colorful pictures, watching short films and discussing them together, listening and trying to understand relevant news. We can cite many other similar language teaching methods.

In conclusion, it can be said that interactive methods are methods based on regular communication, which refers to the system of education and methods with the cooperation and active participation of students. Teaching based on these new innovative methods of teaching foreign languages is giving its positive results. The use of boomerang technology serves to increase the effectiveness of the lesson in explaining large-scale topics in Arabic grammar that combine several rules, such as gender category, point, and adverbial clauses.

REFERENCES:

1. Decision PQ-1875 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov of December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages".
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 23.09.2020 No. ORQ-637.
3. Usmonova N., Azlarov E., Sharipov G. Uzbek language. Textbook for higher educational institutions. - T.: "Teacher", 1991.
4. Ravshan Ishmuhamedov, Maksudjon Yuldashev. "Innovative pedagogical technologies in education", Tashkent-2013; Page 9.
5. Usmonova N., Azlarov E., Sharipov G. Uzbek language. Textbook for higher educational institutions. - T.: "Teacher", 1991
6. Ismailova Sh.K. "Conditions for the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process." UrSU publishing house, Urganch, 2009.